

Strategy of the Directorate General of Customs and Excise in Law Enforcement of Narcotics Smuggling by Internasional Organised Crime

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ABSTRACT: Narcotics are substances that calm the nerves, relieve pain, induce drowsiness or stimulation, cause unconsciousness, and can lead to addiction. The misuse of narcotics is a global problem that threatens the future of nations, particularly through transnational smuggling by organised crime networks. This study examines the role of the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DGCE) in combating narcotics smuggling and explores strategies to optimise its law enforcement functions against increasingly sophisticated international operations. Using a normative juridical method based on legislative analysis, with data collected through literature studies of scientific papers and journals, the research finds that DGCE plays a strategic role in protecting society from the circulation of dangerous goods, including narcotics. As the frontline authority at national borders, DGCE monitors cross-border goods flows and prevents the entry of illegal substances. However, combating narcotics is not solely the responsibility of customs. Effective enforcement requires enhanced inter-agency and international cooperation. DGCE collaborates with the National Narcotics Agency, the police, the Indonesian Navy, and the Food and Drug Supervisory Agency (BPOM) through joint operations and interdiction task forces. Through such synergy, DGCE strengthens its role as a primary gatekeeper against transnational narcotics crimes.

KEYWORDS: Customs, Law Enforcement, Drug Smuggling

I. INTRODUCTION

Drug-related crimes are no longer committed by individuals, but involve many people working together, even organised syndicates with extensive networks that operate in a highly secretive manner.¹

Narcotics are drugs or substances that can calm the nerves, cause unconsciousness or anaesthesia, eliminate pain and suffering, induce drowsiness or stimulation, cause stupor, and can lead to addiction or dependency, and are designated as narcotics by the Minister of Health.²

The current national legal provisions (*ius constitutum*) on narcotics crimes are regulated in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 35 of 2009 on Narcotics (previously regulated through Law Number 22 of 1997 on Narcotics).

The enactment of Law No. 35 of 2009 is expected to bring about reform in the field of criminal law, particularly in terms of combating narcotics crimes, as it is considered more complex in terms of regulating criminal sanctions as a last resort (*ultimum remedium*). Meanwhile, in terms of international cooperation in combating narcotics smuggling, international bodies such as the United Nations (UN) have established the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) convention.³

Drug abuse has become a global problem and has penetrated all levels of society, from the upper, middle and lower classes, and is enjoyed by teenagers, adults and even parents, and its spread has reached villages.⁴

Drug abuse is categorised as an extraordinary crime by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). This is because drugs can destroy an entire generation of a nation. In 2020 alone, there were 269 million users worldwide with 950 types of drugs found. In Indonesia, drug users can come from various backgrounds, including students, university students, workers, civil servants, housewives and even celebrities. The group most vulnerable to drug abuse is those aged 15 to 35 years old, or the millennial

¹ Krido Daru Adwiria dan Ridwan, "Kewenangan Badan Narkotika Nasional Provinsi Sumatera Selatan dalam Mewujudkan Penegakan Hukum Terhadap Tindak Pidana Narkotika," *Lex Lata* 1, no. 3 2019: 280-298

² Mardani, *Penyalahgunaan Narkotika Dalam Perspektif Hukum Islam dan Hukum Pidana Nasional*, Jakarta: PT RajaGrafindo Persada, 2008) Hlm 6

³ Wesly, S. *Kajian Hukum Atas Peran Kepolisian Dalam Pemberantasan Tindak Pidana Narkotika (Studi Kasus di Kepolisian Resort Humbahas)*. *Jurnal Mercatoria*, 7(2), 2014, Hlm179–192

⁴ Hari Sasangka, *Narkotika dan Psikotropika dalam hukum Pidana*, (Bandung: Mandar Maju, 2003) Hlm 3

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generation. Victims of drug abuse occur every day, with 30 drug users dying every day. This situation has caused almost all provinces in Indonesia to experience a drug emergency.⁵

Drug abuse is a global issue and has become the focus of international attention.⁶ The impact of widespread drug abuse in society can damage family relationships, drastically reduce thinking and learning abilities and work productivity, cause antisocial behaviour (maladaptive behaviour), health problems (physical and mental), increase the number of traffic accidents, violence and other crimes. Drug abuse can destroy the foundations of society and the state because the effects of drugs are not only felt by individuals but also by society as a whole. The future of Indonesia depends on its next generation, and if the next generation is damaged, then the country will also be damaged. If this happens, the impact will be enormous on the lives and cultural values of the Indonesian people, which will ultimately weaken national resilience, and this is certainly something that no one wants.

The rapid growth of narcotics-related crimes, coupled with the development of technology today, poses a serious threat to every country in general and Indonesia in particular.⁷

Global data on drug abuse shows an upward trend. According to the 2023 UNODC Report, there are approximately 296 million drug abusers worldwide, equivalent to 5.8% of the global population aged 15-64. In Indonesia, the prevalence of drug abuse in 2023 reached 3.3 million people, or 1.73% of the Indonesian population. According to the Head of the Indonesian National Narcotics Agency (BNN RI), this figure is just the tip of the iceberg and has the potential to increase tenfold. According to the BNN, 27% of drug users are students.⁸

One of the specific features of criminal formulation in Law No. 35 of 2009 on Narcotics is the formulation of specific minimum penalties in addition to general maximum penalties and specific maximum penalties.⁹ Conceptually, the abolition of criminal punishment is closely related to court proceedings, from investigation and prosecution to sentencing. There is also penal mediation.¹⁰

Smuggling is a frequently committed criminal offence. Smuggling is a criminal offence that is on the rise and often occurs in society. This crime has prompted the government to take action to combat the spread or increase of smuggling offences that violate the values and legal norms that apply in society, so that the state has made this crime a punishable offence.¹¹

The modus operandi used by drug smugglers varies greatly, as they are always looking for ways to ensure that the drugs they are carrying can escape the scrutiny and vigilance of officials. These methods include wrapping the drugs in aluminium foil, swallowing them, or hiding them under their shoes so that they will not be detected by officials.

This is a major problem that can occur at any time and in various forms in line with the times. Large quantities of drugs are smuggled into Indonesia from abroad, posing a serious threat to society, which is why supervision by officials and effective law enforcement are needed.

Drug crimes are transnational crimes that cross national borders, causing the development of drug crimes in countries around the world, and need to be eradicated completely. This study aims to determine the development of drug crimes as a form of transnational crime and to determine the role of law enforcement, in this case the DJBC, carried out by the state in dealing with drug crimes.

Transnational organised crime or cross-border crime is organised crime that occurs across national borders and involves groups or networks operating in more than one country to plan and carry out illegal business.¹²

The Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) plays an important role as a law enforcement agency in the prevention and eradication of narcotics in Indonesia. The main role of customs in combating smuggling is as the front line of national border security, monitoring the movement of illegal goods, from prevention to enforcement. Customs and Excise serves as a

⁵ Widha Utami Putri, D. *Indonesia Drugs Report 2022*. (Jakarta: Pusat Penelitian, Data, Informasi Badan Narkotika Nasional Indonesia, 2022).

⁶ Fadhli Muhaimin Ishaq, Depenalisasi Penyalahgunaan Narkotika Studi Komparatif Indonesia dan Portugal, *PAMPAS: Journal Of Criminal Law* Volume 5 Nomor 3, Tahun 2024, Hlm 338.

⁷ Roni Gunawan Raja Gukguk, Nyoman Serikat Putra Jaya, "Tindak Pidana Narkotika Sebagai Transnsional Organized Crime, *Jurnal Pembangunan Indonesia*, Vol. 1(No.3) 2029, Hlm.349

⁸ BNN RI, <https://bnn.go.id/kepala-bnn-ri-banyaknya-jaringan-yang-ditangkap-dan-barang-bukti-yang-disita-bukan-ukuran-keberhasilan-penanganan-narkotika>. Diakses Pada tanggal 14 Agustus 2024

⁹ Katarina Ekowati, Penerapan Sanksi Pidana Minimum Khusus Terhadap Tindak Pidana Narkotika Yang Dilakukan Oleh Anak Di Bawah Umur, *Ius Quia Iustum*, Universitas Islam Indonesia, Hlm. 60

¹⁰ Barda Nawawi Arief, *Mediasi Penal Penyelesaian Pidana Diluar Pengadilan*, Program Magister Hukum, Pascasarjana UNDIP, 2010, hlm. 1-3

¹¹ Nikita Lantu, Selviani Sambali, Liju Zet Viany, *Penegakan Hukum Terhadap Tindak Pidana Penyelundupan Barang Impor Ditinjau dari undang-undang Nomor 17 Tahun 2006 Tentang Kepabeanan*, *Lex-Crimen*, Vol 6 No 1 2024, Samratulangi Hlm 4

¹² https://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kejahatan_terorganisasi_transnasional diakses 20 oktober 2025 Pukul 09.00 WIB.

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community protector, safeguarding the public from the circulation of illegal and dangerous goods through inspections at ports and airports, as well as maritime patrols in border areas.

Given the vastness of Indonesia's customs territory, which is part of the sovereignty of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, the government faces challenges in placing customs and excise officers along the borders to monitor the flow of goods in export and import activities. One of the factors driving smuggling and the current increase in smuggling is advances in information technology, which facilitate international business and trade relations. One of the items that poses a challenge for Indonesia itself is the smuggling of prohibited items.

Smuggling is one of the most common cross-border crimes due to weak surveillance on land, sea, and air routes. Smuggling can be defined as the illegal importation of goods to avoid paying import duties or because the goods are being transported without permission or are prohibited items.¹³

Customs is closely related to law enforcement agencies in efforts to combat smuggling. The main task of customs is to carry out supervision in accordance with the provisions contained in Law Number 17 of 2006, which is an amendment to Law Number 10 of 1995 concerning Customs. This law regulates various matters that form the legal basis for law enforcement officials at the Directorate General of Customs and Excise in carrying out their function as protectors of the community. One of its main focuses is the eradication of smuggling, which describes in detail the criminal act of smuggling and imposes heavier penalties to deter perpetrators of such crimes. There are several law enforcement agencies, but in this study, the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DCBJ) is one of the law enforcement agencies that is the focus of this study.

Based on this description, the author is interested in conducting research on the role of customs and excise in enforcing the law on narcotics smuggling, with the research title: '**Strategy of the Directorate General of Customs and Excise in Law Enforcement of Narcotics Smuggling by International Organised Crime**'.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The method used in this study is normative juridical, which is research using legislation as the subject of study. The data collection technique used by the researcher in this study is a literature study technique, where data is obtained from scientific writings and research in articles and other journals.

Etymologically, the term normative legal research originates from English, while in Dutch it is referred to as *normative juridisch onderzoek*, and in German as *normative juristische recherche*.¹⁴ The types of approaches used in this study are the statutory approach and the conceptual approach. The regulations that form the basis of this research include Law No. 35 of 2009 on Narcotics and Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 17 of 2006 on amendments to Law No. 10 of 1995 on Customs.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Role of the Directorate General of Customs and Excise in Combating Drug Smuggling

Criminal acts develop not only in one country, but also cross the borders of other countries. The circulation of various types of narcotics has become a serious problem faced by the government.

Drug offences and addictive substances are undoubtedly very dangerous to human life; if consumed incorrectly, they can result in death for the user.¹⁵ In recent years, there have been many national crimes that have also crossed international boundaries and space, known as transnational crimes.¹⁶

Drug crimes have become transnational crimes and are smuggled into Indonesia along with other goods. Smuggling is divided into two categories: legal smuggling and illegal smuggling. Legal smuggling involves bringing goods from outside Indonesia into the country or taking goods out of Indonesia to other countries through a specified procedure, namely protected by documents, but the documents do not match the goods being brought in or taken out. Meanwhile, illegal smuggling involves bringing goods in or taking goods out without the protection of documents.¹⁷

Law enforcement agencies, including the Directorate General of Customs and Excise, and the community together have an important role to play in combating drug smuggling.

¹³ Leden Marpaung, *Tindak Pidana Penyelundupan Masalah dan Pemecahan*, (Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 1991), Hlm.3.

¹⁴ Salim HS dan Erlies Septiana Nurbani, *Penerapan Teori Hukum Pada Penelitian Tesis dan Disertasi*, (Jakarta : Raja Grafindo Persada, 2014) Hlm. 18

¹⁵ Eleanora, Fransiska N, *Bahaya Penyalahgunaan Narkoba Serta Usaha Pencegahan dan Penanggulangannya*, Jurnal Hukum, Vol XXV, (No.1), Hlm 439

¹⁶ Roni Gunawan Raja Gukguk, Nyoman Serikat Putra Jaya, *Tindak Pidana Narkotika Sebagai Transnasioanl Organized Crime*, Jurnal Pembangunan Hukum Indonesia Program Studi Magister Ilmu Hukum Volume 1, Nomor 3, Tahun 2019 Hlm 342.

¹⁷ Baharuddin, *Tindak Pidana Ekonomi Pembahasan Tindak Pidana Penyelundupan* (Jakarta: PT. Pradnya Paramita, 2016) Hlm 116

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Customs and Excise is a government agency that plays a vital role in facilitating the smooth flow of exports and imports in customs areas. The government's objective in conducting supervision in accordance with Law No. 17 of 2006, amending Law No. 10 of 1995 on Customs, is to increase state revenue or foreign exchange; to protect domestic products; and to monitor that not all goods can freely enter and exit the Indonesian market or customs areas. To avoid this, the entry and exit of goods from abroad must be accompanied by valid documents through cooperation between Customs and Excise and other agencies, such as port managers, to manage, maintain, and ensure the security and smooth flow of goods entering and leaving customs areas with the aim of preventing smuggling that is detrimental to the state and the smuggling of prohibited goods, in this case narcotics.

The Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) is a government agency under the Ministry of Finance whose main task is to supervise the movement of goods to and from customs areas. The Directorate General of Customs and Excise is also the agency responsible for certain goods that have specified properties and characteristics.¹⁸

Customs plays a strategic role in protecting the public from the threat of dangerous goods, including narcotics. As a community protector, the customs agency carries out its duties to ensure the security and safety of the public from the adverse effects of narcotics abuse.¹⁹

As the front line at customs borders, they have a mandate to monitor the flow of goods across national borders, including preventing the entry of narcotics. This function is carried out through:

1. The implementation of risk management based on the ECO Safe Framework of Standards.
2. The use of non-intrusive inspection technology (e.g. X-ray and gamma ray-based container scanners).
3. International intelligence cooperation through the WCO, Interpol and UNODC networks.
4. Monitoring the integrity of personnel to prevent the involvement of internal conspirators.

Drug smuggling via maritime routes also poses a serious threat to national security and the stability of international trade. The complexity of the global supply chain, coupled with the high volume of maritime trade, provides ample opportunity for organised crime syndicates to smuggle illegal goods, including through rip-on/rip-off methods and with the assistance of internal conspirators at ports. In this context, Customs plays a strategic role as the front line in law enforcement and border surveillance. Efforts that have been made, such as the implementation of risk management, the use of non-intrusive inspection technology, and international intelligence cooperation, have proven to be effective in narrowing the space for perpetrators to operate. However, challenges remain, particularly in terms of personnel integrity and limited surveillance at small ports that are still vulnerable to infiltration by criminal networks.

International trade in this era of globalisation is conducted by all countries around the world, including Indonesia. Indonesia engages in international trade by exporting and importing goods. One of the benefits of this activity is an increase in state revenue. Import and export activities are subject to customs duties, which is why international trade or export and import activities are known as customs and excise.

The agency authorised to carry out supervision and services in the field of customs is the DJBC. The supervision and services provided by the DJBC are measures to increase state revenue from customs. The vertical agency of the DJBC that carries out the supervision and services of the export and import of goods is the Customs and Excise Supervision and Service Bureau (KPPBC).

Customs Law No. 17 of 2006 aims to ensure legal certainty, fairness, transparency, and accountability in public services, support efforts to strengthen and develop the national economy in relation to global trade, the smooth flow of goods, and the improvement of the effectiveness of supervision and services as well as the flow of goods entering and leaving the Indonesian customs area and the movement of certain goods within the Indonesian customs area, as well as strengthening the prevention and eradication of smuggling.²⁰

Customs supervision of narcotics smuggling began with the fact that narcotics trafficking causes significant losses to the state. In addition to potentially weakening the state by undermining its human resources, narcotics crime is believed to be part of the underground economy. Drug abuse is an underground activity that can cause financial losses to the state in terms of costs incurred due to disruption to the social, economic, order and security sectors.²¹

To that end, customs and other agencies are working to prevent and eradicate the illegal distribution and abuse of narcotics, enhance national and international cooperation in the prevention and handling of transnational crime, and improve surveillance capacity and the effectiveness of law enforcement based on five pillars, namely follow the goods, follow the money, follow the transporter, follow the documents, and follow the people.

¹⁸ Nurhalija Sitompul, Zuhri M., *Peran Bea Cukai dalam Efektivitas Pelayanan Ekspor Impor (Studi pada KPPBC TMP C Teluk Nibung)*, Jurnal kolaboratif dan sains, Volume 05, Nomor 06, Juni 2022, Hlm 292.

¹⁹ <https://www.beacukai.go.id/berita/tangkal-penyelundupan-narkoba-bea-cukai-cegah-7-4-ton-narkoba-masuk-indonesia.html> diakses 8 November 2025 Pukul 04.00 WIB

²⁰ Ibid Hlm 293

²¹ Official bea dan cukai, <https://www.beacukai.go.id/berita/tangkal-penyelundupan-narkoba-bea-cukai-cegah-7-4-ton-narkoba-masuk-indonesia.html> diakses 8 November 2025 Pukul 04.00 WIB

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Eradicating the circulation of narcotics continues to be a major issue and a national priority, as it has a devastating impact on the younger generation, social stability, and national security. The Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJBC) has a primary responsibility for the effectiveness of narcotics enforcement as it is at the forefront of tackling narcotics smuggling, given that customs is at the forefront of monitoring the entry and exit of goods across national borders.

Optimisation of the Directorate General of Customs and Excise in law enforcement against high levels of narcotics smuggling by international organised crime.

This study is based on several interrelated main theories. Law Enforcement Theory is used to explain the role of Customs as law enforcement officers at the border in preventing, detecting, and prosecuting violations, particularly drug smuggling. This theory emphasises the importance of a combination of effective prevention, detection, and prosecution to suppress cross-border crime. Furthermore, Organised Crime Theory is used to understand the structure, strategies, and modus operandi of narcotics syndicates that operate like criminal enterprises with global networks, including the use of maritime routes as the main distribution channels.

Narcotics in Indonesia are known as narcotics, which means anaesthetics. According to Law No. 22 of 1995, which was amended by Law No. 30 of 2009 on Narcotics, Article 1 defines narcotics as substances or drugs derived from synthetic or semi-synthetic plants that cause a decrease or alteration in consciousness, loss of sensation, reduction or elimination of pain, and can lead to dependence.²²

Various types of narcotics in various forms and methods of use have spread rapidly in our country. The use and even distribution of narcotics has increased over time. The problem is that nearly 90 percent of narcotics users are young people.

Organised crime, as defined in Article 1(6) of Regulation of the Chief of the Indonesian National Police No. 7 of 2009 concerning the reporting system for disturbances to public security and order, is organised crime whose area of operation covers several countries, impacting the political, governmental, socio-cultural and economic interests of a country and is global in nature.²³

Prevention or control of narcotics abuse is an effort undertaken in order to enforce the law against the use, production and illegal distribution of narcotics, which can be carried out by everyone, including individuals, communities and the state.²⁴

The rise in cases of narcotics smuggling that have been successfully seized shows that Indonesia is increasingly being targeted by international drug syndicates. Indonesia is considered a lucrative market for drug trafficking. One of the reasons for this is that Indonesia is considered a great market with good prices.²⁵

Smuggling is a problem that can occur at any time, and the forms of smuggling vary greatly in line with the times and the reasons for smuggling are also very diverse. A particularly dangerous form of smuggling is the large-scale smuggling of narcotics from abroad into Indonesia, which poses a serious threat to society. Therefore, it is hoped that airport and seaport officials, members of the community, the police, and the National Narcotics Agency, as the authorities responsible for preventing and prosecuting such cases, will exercise vigilance.²⁶

The regulation of narcotics trade in international law is governed by the United Nations Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs 1961, which was amended in 1972. This convention is essentially intended to create a single international convention that is acceptable to all countries and replace separate international regulations on the control of narcotics abuse. The second form of agreement is to improve methods of controlling the circulation of narcotics and limit their use specifically for medical purposes and scientific research, and to ensure international cooperation in controlling the circulation of narcotics in order to achieve the goal of stopping the trade and smuggling of narcotics.

International legal regulations concerning the illicit trafficking of narcotics were first formulated in the United Nations Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs of 1961, which was subsequently amended in 1972 with the Protocol on Amendments to the United Nations Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs of 1961. Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs in 1961, which was subsequently amended in 1972 with the Protocol amending the United Nations Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs of 1961.

²² Setyawati dkk, 2015, Buku seri bahaya Narkoba jilid 1(Surakarta : Tirta Asih Jaya) Hlm. 2

²³ Riza Alifianto Kurniawan, *Kejahatan Terorganisasi Pelaku Tindak Pidana Narkotika*, (Surabaya: Airlangga University Press, 2023) Hlm 8

²⁴ Hariyanto, Bayu P. *Pencegahan Dan Pemberantasan Peredaran Narkoba Di Indonesia*, Jurnal Daulat Hukum, Vol.1,(No.1), 2018, Hlm, 210.

²⁵ R Makbul Padmanagara, "Kejahatan Internasional, Tantangan Dan Upaya Pemecahan", (Majalah Interpol Indonesia, 2007) Hlm 58

²⁶ Wilhelmus Renyaan, Yulianus Pabassing, Muhammad Rijal Taha, *Tinjauan Yuridis Penyelundupan dan Peredaran narkotika Melalui Jasa Expedisi Pengiriman Barang*, Jurnal Umel Mandiri, Sekolah tinggi ilmu Hukum Umel Mandiri, Jayapura Hlm 200

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The difference between the United Nations Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs and the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organised Crime is that the United Nations Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs was originally established with the intention of:

- 1) Improving a strategy for monitoring the circulation of narcotics and also limiting their use, allowing them to be used only for medical purposes and for the development of science;
- 2) Ensuring international cooperation through a strategy for monitoring the circulation of narcotics.²⁷

Optimising the role of customs in preventing drug smuggling is carried out through a comprehensive strategy that includes strengthening supervisory functions, enhancing inter-agency synergy, utilising technology and active community participation. Customs plays a role as a community protector by preventing dangerous goods, including drugs, from entering Indonesian territory. This includes strict surveillance at entry points, conducting intensive surveillance at land, sea and air borders, which are often used as routes for narcotics smuggling, as well as routine patrols, namely conducting regular sea and land patrols to guard the vast and smuggling-prone border areas.²⁸

Enhancing synergy between agencies and internationally in combating narcotics is not the sole responsibility of customs, but requires collaboration with other law enforcement agencies. Cooperation with the National Narcotics Agency, the police, the Indonesian Navy, and the Food and Drug Supervisory Agency (BPOM) through joint operations and the formation of an interdiction task force, while international collaboration is achieved through participation in joint operations such as the Joint Task Force on Narcotics (JTF on Narcotics) with other countries to tackle transnational crime and demonstrate commitment on the global stage.

The synergy of the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DJKB) in combating narcotics smuggling is crucial and must be realised through active and continuous collaboration with other law enforcement agencies, particularly the National Narcotics Agency and the police. Integrated surveillance is strengthened with the support of other agencies, given the vast geographical area of Indonesia, which has the potential to become a smuggling route.

CONCLUSIONS

Drug smuggling has evolved into a serious transnational organised crime that threatens Indonesia's national security, economic stability, and the future of its younger generation. As narcotics syndicates increasingly utilise global supply chains, maritime routes, and sophisticated concealment methods, Indonesia has become a strategic target and lucrative market. The Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DGCE), as the frontline authority at national borders, therefore holds a central and strategic role in preventing and eradicating narcotics smuggling.

Based on Law No. 17 of 2006 concerning Customs and related narcotics legislation, DGCE is mandated to supervise the movement of goods entering and leaving customs areas, ensure compliance with documentation requirements, and prevent the circulation of prohibited goods, including narcotics. Its role extends beyond revenue collection to safeguarding society from dangerous substances that undermine public health and national resilience. Through risk management based on international standards, the utilisation of non-intrusive inspection technologies such as X-ray and container scanners, and intelligence cooperation via networks such as WCO, Interpol, and UNODC, DGCE strengthens border control and narrows opportunities for organised criminal networks.

However, effective law enforcement against narcotics smuggling cannot rely solely on Customs. The complexity of organised crime—often involving structured syndicates, maritime smuggling, rip-on/rip-off methods, and internal conspirators—requires integrated and sustained collaboration. Synergy with the National Narcotics Agency, the Indonesian National Police, the Indonesian Navy, BPOM, and other relevant institutions is essential. Joint operations, interdiction task forces, intelligence sharing, and the application of the “follow the goods, follow the money, follow the transporter, follow the documents, and follow the people” approach enhance enforcement effectiveness.

Optimisation of DGCE's role must therefore focus on strengthening supervision capacity, improving personnel integrity, expanding surveillance at vulnerable small ports, enhancing technological capability, and deepening national and international cooperation. Through comprehensive and coordinated strategies, the Directorate General of Customs and Excise can maximise its function as the primary gatekeeper in combating transnational narcotics smuggling and protecting the Indonesian people from its devastating impacts.

²⁷ Rukmana,A.Indra. *Perdagangan Narkotika dalam Perspektif Hukum Pidana Internasional*,Jurnal Ilmu Hukum Legal Opinion,Vol.2,(Vol.1) 2014, ,Hlm 8

²⁸ <https://www.beacukai.go.id/berita/-siaran-pers-optimalisasi-pengawasan-bea-cukai-dorong-kinerja-apbn-regional-jawa-timur> diakses8 november 2025 Pukul. 05.00 WIB

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RECOMMENDATION

To strengthen the effectiveness of narcotics smuggling prevention, the Directorate General of Customs and Excise (DGCE) should prioritise the enhancement of surveillance capacity at high-risk entry points, particularly small ports and remote maritime borders that remain vulnerable to organised crime infiltration. Investment in advanced non-intrusive inspection technology, integrated data analytics, and real-time cargo tracking systems should be expanded to improve early detection and risk profiling.

Institutional integrity must also be reinforced through strict internal monitoring, periodic audits, integrity testing, and continuous professional training to prevent internal conspiracies. Capacity-building programmes focusing on intelligence analysis and organised crime investigation should be intensified.

Furthermore, inter-agency coordination must be institutionalised through permanent joint task forces, shared intelligence platforms, and standardised operating procedures among DGCE, the National Narcotics Agency, the Police, the Navy, and BPOM. International cooperation should be deepened through active participation in global enforcement networks and joint cross-border operations.

Finally, public awareness and community participation should be encouraged to support early reporting and prevention efforts, ensuring a comprehensive national response to transnational narcotics crimes.

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